
Retaining Talent: Key to Organizational Success

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ABSTRACT

Employee retention is a challenging task for management, especially in a competitive environment. Employees are valuable assets to any organization. To retain skilled and talented employees, a company should foster a conducive environment and implement effective strategies. This includes systematic evaluation of employees performance and timely feedback, recognition and growth opportunities.

Introduction

It is challenging for an organization to survive if its top performers leave. Therefore, retaining talented and committed employees is crucial. Organizations need loyal individuals who work with dedication toward achieving organizational goals.

While many view employee retention simply as the effort to keep employees within the workforce, it is more accurately seen as a set of strategies rather than just an outcome. In today's competitive environment, companies are shifting from mere survival to striving for excellence. This shift has led to increased demand for the most skilled and capable employees, which, if not managed well, can result in a significant and uncontrollable loss of talent.

Underlying causes of workforce reduction often include low employee morale, unclear career progression, lack of recognition, and weak employee-manager relationships. In some cases, employees leave due to dissatisfaction with their working conditions.

Effective employee retention involves a strategic and consistent effort by employers to build a positive and supportive work environment. This includes implementing policies and practices that address the diverse needs of employees. A well-designed retention strategy not only reduces turnover but also serves as a powerful tool for attracting new talent.

The study's objectives

- To study employee retention
- Retention of skilled labours
- Appraise holding with specialists

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Table 4.1 Organizational Development

Factors	No of Respondents	Percentage
Never	0	0
Sometimes	10	10%
Mostly	30	30%
Always	60	60%

Figure 4.1 Organizational Development

Interpretation

Table 4.1 shows that 60% of the employees in ABC Motors always ponder that employee retention lead to organizational development. No employees have expressed never parameter.

Table 4.2 Reward, Recognition and Respect

Factors	No of Respondents	Percentage
Never	5	5%
Sometimes	28	28%
Mostly	20	20%
Always	47	47%

Figure 4.2 Reward, Recognition and Respect

Interpretation

"According to Table 4.2, 47% of the employees consistently receive all three R's—reward, recognition, and respect—in their workplace. On the other hand, only 5% of the employees report not receiving any of these three elements."

Table 4.3 Recognition for Performance

Factors	No of Respondents	Percentage
Never	0	0%
Sometimes	15	15%
Mostly	45	45%
Always	40	40%

Figure4.3 Recognition for Performance

Interpretation

Figure 4.3 indicates a slight variation in the analysis. Mostly 45% employees are getting deserved recognition in their performance. 40% employees are always getting deserved recognition in their performance. 15% employees are sometimes only getting deserved recognition in their performance. Nobody opted the never parameter.

Table 4.4 Incentives & Perks

Factors	No of Respondents	Percentage
Never	2	2%
Sometimes	8	8%

Mostly	20	20%
Always	70	70%

Figure 4.4 Incentives & Perks

Interpretation

From the above figure 4.4 it is interrupted that 70% of the personnel are happy with Incentives & Perks offered by the company. It shows a positive approach for employee retention in the organization.

Table 4.5 Solution to Grievances

Factors	No of Respondents	Percentage
Never	5	5%
Sometimes	10	10%
Mostly	35	35%
Always	50	50%

Figure 4.5 Solution to Grievances

Interpretation

Figure 4.4 shows whether the management try to give solution to their grievances? 50% of the participants are convinced with the involvement of management. 5% of staff expressed dissatisfaction on management approach.

Table 4.6 Personal Accomplishment in work

Factors	No of Respondents	Percentage
Yes	90	90%
No	10	10%

Figure 4.6 Personal Accomplishment in work

Interpretation

Figure 4.6 represent Personal Accomplishment in work. 90% of the workers were felt Personal Accomplishment in their work. It shows the chance for employee retention is very high. Only 10% of the workers were not happy in their work.

Table 4.7 Promotion of Creativity

Factors	No of Respondents	Percentage
Yes	90	90%
No	10	10%

Figure 4.7 Promotion of Creativity

Interpretation

From Figure 4.6 90% of the employees were suggested the organization advocates and support their creativity. Only 10% have the negative opinion.

Table 4.8 Communication of company goals

Factors	No of Respondents	Percentage
Yes	93	93%

No	7	7%
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Figure 4.8 Communication of company goals

Interpretation

Figure 4.7 indicates the communication of company goals. 93% are suggested that they receive clear understanding of its objectives. It will leads to the active participation of workers for doing their work.

Table 4.9 Co-ordination among workers

Factors	No of Respondents	Percentage
Yes	97	97%
No	3	3%

Figure 4.9 Co-ordination among workers

Interpretation

From the above figure it was analyzed that co-ordination among workers are good. It will create a better working environment. And it will also leads to the growth of the company.

Table 4.10 Respect to the employees

Factors	No of Respondents	Percentage
Yes	87	87%
No	13	13%

Figure 4.10 Respect to the employees

Interpretation

Table 4.10 shows the respect given to the employees. 87% are expressed they are getting good respect. 13% are expressed they are not getting deserved respect for their work.

Table 4.11 Training and Development Program

Factors	No of Respondents	Percentage
Yes	85	85%
No	15	15%

Figure 4.11 Training and Development Program

Interpretation

From the above mentioned table it is observed a considerable share of the employees (85%) are benefited with the training and development program provided by the company. Only 15% of the employees have negative opinion to the training and development program.

Table 4.12 Employees Suggestion

Factors	No of Respondents	Percentage
Strongly Agree	68	68%
Agree	20	20%
Neutral	8	8%
Strongly Disagree	4	4%
Disagree	0	0%

Figure 4.12 Employees Suggestion

Interpretation

The preceding table was clear that 68%, team members strongly affirm that their suggestions are considered. No employees disagree. It indicates a democratic system is implemented in the organization.

Table 4.13 Appreciation for work

Factors	No of Respondents	Percentage
Strongly Agree	15	15%
Agree	50	50%
Neutral	25	25%
Strongly Disagree	5	5%
Disagree	5	5%

Figure 4.13 Appreciation for work

Interpretation

The top figure 4.13, it is analyzed that there is a consensus among 50% of employees agreed they are getting appreciation for their work. 25% of the employees are no opinion.

Table 4.14 Management Tool

Factors	No of Respondents	Percentage
Strongly Agree	15	15%
Agree	40	40%
Neutral	30	30%
Strongly Disagree	10	10%
Disagree	5	5%

Figure 4.14 Management Tool

Interpretation

From figure 4.41 it is revealed that 40% employees agreed that management tool helped them to achieve their goals. But 30% of the employees are neutral. Only 5% of the employees disagreed.

Table 4.15 Encourages Creativity

Factors	No of Respondents	Percentage
Strongly Agree	60	60%
Agree	20	20%
Neutral	9	9%

Strongly Disagree	8	8%
Disagree	3	3%

Figure 4.15 Encourages Creativity

Interpretation

From the figure 60% employees are in agreement that company encourages and support their creativity. 20% of the workforce have no opinion. Only 3% disagreed. The analysis shows ABC Motors providing opportunity for creativity.

Table 4.16 Working Environment

Factors	No of Respondents	Percentage
Highly Satisfied	20	20%
Satisfied	60	60%
Neutral	9	9%
Highly Dissatisfied	8	8%
Dissatisfied	3	3%

Figure 4.16 Working Environment

Interpretation

The Table indicates that 60% of employees are satisfied with their work environment. Additionally 20% of employees reported being highly satisfied. A positive work environment contributes to greater employee engagement and active participation in on organizational activities.

Table 4.17 Job Satisfaction

Factors	No of Respondents	Percentage
Highly Satisfied	35	35%
Satisfied	45	45%
Neutral	10	10%
Highly Dissatisfied	8	8%
Dissatisfied	2	2%

Figure 4.17 Job Satisfaction

Interpretation

It is interrupted that there is only a slight difference between the number of employees who were satisfied and those who are highly satisfied with their job. While 45% of employees report being satisfied, 35% are highly satisfied. Only 2% of employees expressed dissatisfaction with their job.

Table 4.18 Welfare Measures

Factors	No of Respondents	Percentage
Highly Satisfied	45	45%
Satisfied	20	20%
Neutral	25	25%
Highly Dissatisfied	10	10%
Dissatisfied	0	0%

Figure 4.18 Welfare Measures

Interpretation

The figure above clearly shows that 45% of employees are highly satisfied with the welfare measures implemented by the organization. Notably, no employees expressed dissatisfaction regarding the welfare initiative taken by the company.

19 Carrier Development

Factors	No of Respondents	Percentage
Highly Satisfied	45	45%
Satisfied	35	35%
Neutral	13	13%
Highly Dissatisfied	7	7%
Dissatisfied	0	0%

Figure 4.19 Carrier Development

Interpretation

In ABC motors analyzed that majority laborers enjoyed their carrier development. The company is providing ample opportunity for carrier development. In the survey nobody is dissatisfied.

Table 4.20 Supportive provisions from Organization

Factors	Number Respondents	Percentage
Highly Satisfied	15	15%
Satisfied	45	45%
Moderate	25	25%
Highly Dis satisfied	5	5%

Not satisfied	10	10%
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Figure 4.20 Amenities provided by Organization

Interpretation

The figure above indicates that only 45% of the employees are satisfied with the facilities made available in the organization. Additionally 10% of the employees expressed dissatisfaction, while 5% reported being highly dis satisfied with organization facilities.

Table 4.21 To stay with the organization

Factors	No of Respondents	Percentage
Salary	20	20%
Working environment	40	40%
Career development	20	20%
Loyalty towards the company	15	15%
Job security	5	5%

Figure 4.21 To continue being a part of organization

Interpretation

It is interpreted that first priority to remain in ABC motors is good working environment. salary and carrier development comes second, loyalty is third and job security is last.

Table 4.22 Income of Employees

Income	No of Respondents	Percentage
Below 5000	8	8%
5100-10000	32	32%
10100-15000	45	45%
Above 15000	5	15%

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Figure 4.22 Income of Employees

Interpretation

From above figure it is clear that 45% employees are getting the salary between 10100-15000. 8% employees are getting salary of below 5000.

Table 4.23 Gender

Factors	No of Respondents	Percentage
Male	78	78%
Female	22	22%

Figure 4.23 Gender

Interpretation

Male: 78%

Female: 22%

CHAPTER 5**HYPOTHESIS**

Ho: No significant different in the average level of satisfaction in the facilities supplied by organization among different genders.

Group Statistics					
	Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Perception of organizational facilities in terms of employee satisfaction	Male	78	3.5769	.84545	.09573
	Female	22	3.4545	1.53459	.32718

Independent sample test							
		Levene's test for equality of variances		t-test for equality of means			
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig.(2-tailed)	Mean Difference
Satisfaction with facilities provided by the organization	Equal variances are assumed	34.895	.000	.491	98	.625	.12238
	Equal variances were not assumed			.359	24.700	.723	.12238

The test result (with equal variance not assumed) shows t statistic of .359 with 24.7000 degree of freedom. The corresponding two tailed p value is 0.723, which is greater than 0.05. Therefore, we can accept the null hypothesis at 5% level of importance, which means average level of satisfaction in the facilities are equal among different gender.

Ho: Here not that much significant difference in the average level of satisfaction in the facilities proposed by the organization among different income groups.

ANOVA					
Satisfaction with amenities supplied by enterprise					
	Sum of Squares	DF	Average Square	F	Sig.
Among Groups	67.328	3	22.443	57.574	.000
Within Groups	37.422	96	.390		
Total	104.750	99			

This is the table that shows outcome of ANOVA and whether the difference in a group is statistically validated. We can see significance level 0.000 ($p = .000$), which is below 0.05 and, therefore dis confirmed null hypothesis. A statistical meaningful variation exists in the average satisfaction level with the facilities provided by the organization across different income group.

H₀: Not that much notable importance association between gender and feel of personal accomplishment in works.

Gender * Personal accomplishment

Crosstabulation

Count

		Personal accomplishment		Total
		Yes	No	
Gender	Male	73	5	78
	Female	17	5	22
Total		90	10	100

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (1-sided)

Pearson Chi-Square	5.076 ^a	1	.024		
Continuity Correction ^b	3.425	1	.064		
Likelihood Ratio	4.289	1	.038		
Fisher's Exact Test				.039	.039
Linear-by-Linear Association	5.026	1	.025		
N of Valid Cases	100				

The test statistics shows that Pearson Chi-Square value 5.076^a and two-tailed significant value is 0.024 (p -value=.024) which is lesser than .05. Based on the analysis, the null hypothesis is rejected, which means that there is an association between gender and personal accomplishment at worksite.

FINDINGS

1. It is observed that employees are expecting more rewards, recognition and respect.
2. The Recognition for performance seems to be comparatively less.
3. The incentives and perks provided by the company is appreciably good.
4. Employees grievance should be given due consideration and timely solutions.
5. Company goals are clearly communicated.
6. Co-ordination among the workers are good.
7. There should be more appreciation for the works done by the employees.

CONCLUSION

Management could have effectively minimize human resource turnover by implementing different retention strategies. It may be included by ensuring fair recruitment and selection process, providing comprehensive orientation programmes including flexible working hours, easy communication to the superiors and management, redressal of employees grievances, good working atmosphere should be provided, fair incentive system should be implemented. Employees motivation is another factor for retention. If employees are highly motivated, their turn over can be reduced. The performance should be recognized. They can be provided with regular training and career development programme. Promotion opportunities may be offered. Performance appraisal should be implemented.

Top Level Management should have a better relationship with the labour. Employee turnover is primarily driven by internal factors rather than external factors. It indicates that major cause of labour

attrition are with in the organization. This problem can be effectively solved by improving existing HR policies and practices. The top management should be flexible for making changes to control the personnel retention.

SUGGESTIONS

1. The company needs to implement a bit more better strategy for employee retention.
2. The management tool should be more flexible.
3. The company should provide more facilities to the employees.
4. More carrier development opportunities should be provided to the employees.
5. The tools to achieve the organizational goals should be modified.
6. Programs for job satisfaction should be implemented.
7. Employee's suggestion should be given more consideration.
8. Employee's creativity should be given more space for implementation.
9. The salary scheme should be modified.
10. The strategy to improve loyalty towards organization should be more pleasing to the employees.

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